

ECOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF GERMAN WORDS IN THE BOSNIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Ecolinguistics is a new paradigm within sociolinguistic research that emerged during the 1990s. This discipline examines interactions between languages as well as the relationships between languages and their social and physical environments, similar to how ecology studies the interdependence of living organisms. This paper explores the influence of the German language on the Bosnian language, with a particular focus on the semantic adaptations of German words within the Bosnian linguistic system. The analysis centers on the conceptual field of nutrition and health, investigating how foreign German words undergo the process of adaptation. The goal is to describe the transformations that occur from the moment of "borrowing" a word to the formation of its basic form, known in linguistics as a replica, as well as how these words continue to change during their integration into the Bosnian language. Additionally, the paper includes an analysis of the frequency of Germanisms in the context of nutrition and health, providing insight into their prevalence and usage in contemporary Bosnian. This research contributes to the understanding of linguistic and cultural interactions between languages, emphasizing the significance of semantic adaptations in multilingual contexts.

Keywords: *ecolinguistics, German language, Bosnian language, semantic adaptations*

EKOLINGVISTIČKA ANALIZA NJEMAČKIH RIJEČI U BOSANSKOM JEZIKU

Apstrakt

Ekolingvistika je nova paradigma u sociolingvističkim istraživanjima koja se pojavila tokom 1990-ih. Ova disciplina ispituje interakcije između jezika, kao i odnose između jezika i njihovog društvenog i fizičkog okruženja, slično kao što ekologija proučava međuzavisnost živih organizama. Ovaj rad istražuje uticaj njemačkog jezika na bosanski jezik, sa posebnim fokusom na semantičke adaptacije njemačkih riječi unutar bosanskog jezičkog sistema. Analiza se fokusira na konceptualno polje ishrane i zdravlja, istražujući kako strane njemačke riječi prolaze kroz proces adaptacije. Cilj je da se opišu transformacije koje se dešavaju od trenutka „pozajmljivanja“ riječi do formiranja njenog osnovnog oblika, poznatog u lingvistici kao replika, kao i kako se ove reči nastavljaju mijenjati tokom njihove integracije u bosanski jezik. Pored toga, rad uključuje analizu učestalosti germanizama u kontekstu ishrane i zdravlja, pružajući uvid u njihovu rasprostranjenost i upotrebu u savremenom bosanskom jeziku. Ovo istraživanje doprinosi razumijevanju jezičkih i kulturnih interakcija između jezika, naglašavajući značaj semantičkih adaptacija u višejezičnim kontekstima.

Ključne riječi: *ekolingvistika, nemački jezik, bosanski jezik, semantičke adaptacije*

INTRODUCTION

Following the global economic crisis of 2008 Languages are dynamic systems that continuously evolve and change under the influence of various factors, including social transformations, historical circumstances, and contact with other languages. Ecolinguistics, which studies language within its ecological and social context, provides a new framework for analyzing linguistic adaptation processes in multicultural and multilingual environments.

The German language has had a long-standing influence on the Bosnian language, primarily due to historical ties and interactions in trade, administration, and culture. This influence was particularly pronounced during the Austro-Hungarian rule (1878–1918), when a significant number of German words entered the Bosnian language, becoming an integral part of everyday speech, especially in the domains of food, health, technology, and craftsmanship.

This study focuses on an ecolinguistic analysis of German loanwords in the Bosnian language, examining how these words have been integrated, modified, and adapted to the phonological, morphological, and semantic structures of Bosnian. The analysis is based on the conceptual fields of food and health, as these areas are particularly rich in German borrowings.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

The theoretical framework of this study is based on Rudolf Filipović's (1986) model of linguistic borrowing, which divides the process of language adaptation into primary and secondary phases. According to this model:

- Primary adaptation encompasses phonological, morphological, and semantic changes that occur in the early stages of word adoption. These modifications allow the borrowed word to conform to the structural rules of the recipient language, facilitating its use in both spoken and written communication.
- Secondary adaptation involves the further integration of the borrowed word into the recipient language system, during which changes in meaning, function, and frequency of use may occur across different contexts. This phase often includes semantic transformations, such as narrowing or expansion of meaning.

From a methodological perspective, this study employs a descriptive-analytical approach to examine German loanwords in the domains of food and health in the Bosnian language. The analysis is based on data collected from multiple sources, including:

- Dictionaries and linguistic studies that document the use of German loanwords,
- Newspaper articles and literary texts, which reflect contemporary language use,
- Conversations with Bosnian speakers, providing insights into the everyday use and semantic nuances of borrowed terms.

This methodological framework enables a comprehensive examination of the process of linguistic adaptation of German loanwords and their functional status in contemporary Bosnian.

BORROWING AND ADAPTATION OF FOREIGN WORDS INTO A NEW LINGUISTIC SYSTEM

The process of borrowing foreign words into a new linguistic system necessarily involves adaptation, which allows these words to conform to the phonological, orthographic, and morphological rules of the recipient language. A borrowed word undergoes modifications to the extent required for integration, leading to potential changes at the phonological, morphological, semantic, and lexical levels (Filipović, 1986).

Adaptation is a gradual and complex process, which develops through primary and secondary changes, distinguishing between primary and secondary adaptation.

Phonological adaptation is the first and unavoidable step, as the phonological systems of the donor and recipient languages rarely align completely. Borrowed words adjust by substituting certain phonemes with their closest equivalents in the recipient language, or through the omission or insertion of phonological elements.

Following phonological adaptation, morphological adjustment occurs, during which the borrowed word adapts its grammatical characteristics to fit the structural rules of the recipient language.

Unlike phonological and morphological adaptation, semantic adaptation pertains to changes in meaning, involving more complex cognitive processes. These changes are closely tied to the way speakers of the recipient language conceptualize borrowed terms. In this sense, the semantic adaptation of German loanwords reflects the interaction between language and thought, making it a distinctive aspect of linguistic integration.

ANALYSIS OF THE ADAPTATION PROCESS OF GERMAN LOANWORDS AT THE SEMANTIC LEVEL

This study focuses on analyzing the process of semantic adaptation of German loanwords in the Bosnian language, encompassing both primary and secondary phases. The most frequently occurring Germanisms from the conceptual field of food and health have been extracted from the corpus for analysis.

These are: *ajnpren* < *Einbrenn* (*roux*), *bešte* < *Besteck* (*cutlery*), *birtija* < *Wirtshaus* (*tavern*), *brezle* ili *brizle* < *Bries* (*sweetbreads*), *buhle* < *Buchteln* (*yeast buns*), *bru* < *Bruch* (*hernia*), *celer* < *Sellerie* (*celery*), *cinkova mast* < *Zinksalbe* (*zinc ointment*), *dinstati* < *dünsten* (*to stew*), *ementaler* < *Emmentaler Käse* (*Emmental cheese*), *escajg* < *Esszeug* (*tableware*), *fasung* < *Fassung* (*packaging*), *faširati* < *fascieren* (*to mince*), *fil* < *Füllung* (*filling*), *filovati* < *füllen* (*to fill*), *flaster* < *Pflaster* (*plaster/band-aid*), *flaša* < *Flasche* (*bottle*), *flašica* < *Fläschchen* (*small bottle*), *flaširanje* < *Flaschenabfüllung* (*bottling*), *flek* < *Fleck* (*stain*), *fras* < *Frass* (*shock/seizure*), *frišak* < *frisch* (*fresh*), *frištik* < *Frühstück* (*breakfast*), *gemišt* < *Gemisch* (*mixed drink*), *geršla* < *Gerste* (*barley*), *giht* < *Gicht* (*gout*), *griz* < *Grieß* (*semolina*), *haringa* < *Hering* (*herring*), *kifla* < *Kipferl* (*crescent roll*), *knedla* < *Knödel* (*dumpling*), *košpica* < *Kernstück* (*seed/kernel*), *krigla* < *Krögel* (*beer mug*), *krofna* < *Krapfen* (*doughnut*), *krompir* < *Kartoffel* (*potato*), *kuga* < *Pest* (*plague*), *kuglof* < *Gugelhupf* (*bundt cake*), *mileram* < *Milchrahm* (*sour cream*), *pakung* <

Packung (package), *pleh* < *Blech* (baking tray/sheet metal), *princes krofne* < *Prinzesskrapfen* (cream puffs), *puter* < *Butter* (butter), *rendgen* < *Röntgen* (X-ray), *verna* < *Röhre* (oven), *ribati* < *reiben* (to grate), *roštilj* < *Rost* (grill), *saft* < *Saft* (juice/sauce), *sala* < *Schmalz* (lard), *senf* < *Senf* (mustard), *supa* < *Suppe* (soup), *šampita* < *Schaumgebäck* (foam pastry), *šarlah* < *Scharlach* (scarlet fever), *šerpa* < *Schöpfer* (cooking pot), *šlag* < *Schlagsahne* (whipped cream), *šmekati* < *schmecken* (to taste), *šnicla* < *Schnitzel* (cutlet), *šnita* < *Schnitte* (slice), *šolja* < *Schale* (cup/bowl), *špajz* < *Speisekammer* (pantry), *špica* < *Spitze* (peak/tip), *šprica* < *Spritze* (syringe), *šporet* < *Sparherd* (stove), *štanglica* < *Stange* (bar/stick), *čokolade* < *Schokolade* (chocolate), *štapić* < *Stäbchen* (stick), *štruca* < *Strutz* (loaf), *šunka* < *Schinken* (ham), *vaga* < *Waage* (scale), *vekna* < *Wecken* (loaf of bread).

In this analysis, we will follow the principles and methods of Rudolf Filipović, who based his approach on Hope's classification system. Filipović adopted this system, adapted it to his own analysis, and further modified it. In his methodology, he emphasizes the need to divide adaptation processes into two phases, stating:

"By applying primary and secondary adaptation at the semantic level, we have established a new classification that meets the requirements of our analysis of semantic changes, particularly in the meaning shifts of loanwords." (Filipović, 1986:161)

Based on the comparison between the model and its replica, Filipović identifies three types of semantic changes:

- Zero semantic extension – the meaning remains unchanged in the recipient language.
- Narrowing of meaning – this can occur as a reduction in the number of meanings (eliminating polysemy) or as a restriction of the semantic field (limiting the word's usage to a more specific context).
- Expansion of meaning – the word acquires new meanings in the recipient language.

Primary adaptation includes: zero semantic extension – no difference in meaning between the model and its replica, narrowing of meaning in number – a shift from multiple meanings to a single meaning, narrowing of the semantic field – a transition from a general meaning to a more specific one.

Secondary adaptation encompasses the expansion of meanings and the broadening of the semantic field. Additionally, in secondary adaptation, changes may occur due to metaphor, metonymy, pejoration, and ellipsis (Sočanac, 1992).

Zero semantic extension

Zero semantic extension occurs when a loanword from German retains the same meaning in Bosnian without undergoing any modifications in its fundamental semantic structure. Filipović refers to this phenomenon as meaning transfer, emphasizing that it most commonly applies to terms with a precisely defined meaning. These include technical terms from various fields such as medicine, nutrition, engineering, construction, sports, and agriculture, as well as names of members of specific ideological, philosophical, and social movements and nouns that denote carriers of certain characteristics or functions.

In the case of German loanwords in the fields of food and health, this type of adaptation is predominant—most borrowed words retain a well-defined meaning, with only one specific sense being transferred. Instances where a loanword retains multiple meanings from the source language are rare.

Based on this, zero semantic extension can be further divided into two categories.

- The first group consists of models with one assumed meaning, such as in our corpus:

birtija < *Wirtshaus*¹¹⁵ (*gostionica* = *tavern*), *brizle* < *Briesel* (*pečene janjeće ili teleće prsne žlijezde* = *sweetbreads*), *bruh* < *Bruch* (*razg. kila* = *hernia*), *buhla* < *Buchtel* (*domaći i pekarski kolač od dizanog tijesta* = *yeast bun*), *cinkova mast* < *Zinksalbe* (*mast koja sadrži cinkov oksid* = *zinc ointment*), *ementaler* < *Emmentaler* (*tvrdi sir* = *hard cheese*), *flaša* < *Flasche* (*boca* = *bottle*), *geršl* < *Gerste* (*jelo od ječma* = *barley dish*), *giht* < *Gicht* (*bolest koja zahvata tkivo oko malih zglobova* = *gout*), *griz* < *Grieß* (*krupno samljevena pšenica* = *semolina*), *haringa* < *Hering* (*vrsta ribe* = *herring*), *kifla* < *Kipfel* (*pecivo u obliku polumjeseca* = *crescent roll*), *knedla* < *Knödel* (*okruglo oblikovano i eventualno punjeno tijesto od krompira* = *dumpling*), *krigla* < *Krügel* (*čša iz koje se pije pivo* = *beer mug*), *kuga* < *Koge* (*zarazna bolest* = *plague*), *kuglof* < *Gugelhupf* (*vrsta kolača* = *bundt cake*), *pakung* < *Packung* (*vrsta kure za kosu* = *hair treatment pack*), *rendgen* < *Röntgen* (*gerät*) (*aparatus za snimanje tijela pomoću rendgenskih zraka* = *X-ray machine*), *šarlah* < *Scharlach* (*zarazna dječja bolest* = *scarlet fever*), *šprica* < *Spritze* (*pribor u obliku staklenog cilindra s klipom i šupljom iglom za ubrizgavanje lijekova* = *syringe*).

- The second group consists of models with two or more assumed meanings: *pleh* < *Blech* (*lim; tepsija za pečenje* = *sheet metal; baking tray*), *flaster* < *Pflaster* (*med. samoljepljivi ovoj za zaštitu ozlijeđenog mjesta; betonski opločnici pren. onaj koji se prilijepe uz koga* = *adhesive bandage; paving stones; someone who sticks to another person*), *flek* < *Fleck* (*mrlja i potamnjeno mjesto; sjena na plućima; zakrpka, npr. na cipelama* = *stain and darkened spot; lung shadow; patch, e.g., on shoes*), *cug* < *Zug* (*vlak; šah potez kombinirao sa iz – iz cuga znači odjednom* = *train; chess move; in one go*), *špic* < *Spitze* (*vrh; vrhunac sezone ili sl.; jezgro koštuničavog voća i vrsta psa* = *peak; peak season or similar; stone fruit kernel and a breed of dog*).

Narrowing of meaning

Narrowing of meaning is one of the most common phenomena in the process of semantic adaptation of foreign words. When comparing German loanwords in

¹¹⁵ The dictionaries used in translating Germanisms into Bosnian are: *Dictionary of Bosnian* by Ibrahim Čedić et al., *Dictionary of Bosnian* by a group of authors Senahid Halilović, Ibrahim Palić and Amela Šehović and the *Great Dictionary of Foreign Words* by Klaić Bratoljub.

Bosnian and German, it is evident that many words in German have multiple meanings, whereas in Bosnian, only one meaning is typically retained—usually the one most necessary for designating a specific concept or object. This process leads to the specialization of meaning and is referred to as narrowing of meaning.

Narrowing of meaning can manifest in two ways:

1. Reduction in the number of meanings – when a loanword in Bosnian retains only one of the multiple possible meanings it has in German.
2. Restriction of the semantic field – when, in addition to a reduction in the number of meanings, the word is used in a more limited context than in the source language, resulting in double narrowing.

The analysis of the corpus in this study confirms that narrowing of meaning most commonly occurs in both forms, with only one specific meaning of the original word being transferred, as demonstrated in the following examples:

bešteak < Besteck (cutlery, Duden 1/3)¹¹⁶

The meaning of the word *das Besteck* in German: 1. cutlery (*Essbesteck*) 2. A set of instruments composed for a specific medical purpose (*für einen bestimmten medizinischen Zweck zusammengestellter Satz von Instrumenten*) 3. position of a ship at sea (*Ortsbestimmung eines Schiffes auf See*)

fasung < Fassung (food tracking, Duden 6b/6)

The meaning of the word *die Fassung* in German: 1a. edge - often artistically made - for the purpose of attaching an object (*der Befestigung eines Gegenstands in etwas dienende, oft kunstvoll ausgearbeitete Umrandung, Einfassung*) 1b. a hoop used to capture and collect water, eg on a well (*dem Auffangen, Sammeln von Wasser (besonders eines Brunnens) dienende [ausgemauerte] Umrandung*) 1c. Screw or clamp holder (*Haltevorrichtung zum Festschrauben oder Festklemmen*) 2. linguistic form; formulation (*sprachliche Form, Ausformung; Formulierung*) 3. color painting or gilding of wood or stone sculpture 4. self-control (*Selbstbeherrschung*) 5. the grasping (*das Ergreifen*) 6. large quantity (*Ladung - größere Menge*)

fil < Füllung (stuffing, mixture Duden 2a/3)

The meaning of the word *die Füllung* in German: 1. filling (*das Füllen*) 2a. mixture, which is added to a particular dish for enrichment (*Masse, die zur Anreicherung in bestimmte Speisen hineingefüllt wird*) 2b. dental filling (*Masse, die den Hohlraum in einem Zahn nach dem Ausbohren ausfüllt*) 2c. material in mattresses, quilts, pillows (*Material in Matratzen, Federbetten, Kissen*) 3. door panel (*Türfüllung*)

rerina < Röhre (oven, the part of the stove where groceries are baked, Duden 3/6)

The meaning of the word *die Röhre* in German: 1. long cylindrical hollow body [with smaller diameter], mainly used for transporting gases or liquids (*langer zylindrischer Hohlkörper [mit geringerem Durchmesser], der vor allem dazu dient, Gase oder Flüssigkeiten weiterzuleiten*) 2. a small tubular vessel (*kleiner röhrenförmiger Behälter*) 3. baking and frying tube (*Back-, Bratröhre*) 4a. Electronic tubes, in

¹¹⁶ The first number indicates which meaning is recorded in the *Duden Universalwörterbuch dictionary*, and the second number indicates how many meanings the dictionary lists under the entry of that model. This data is relevant in order to notice a narrowing in the number. All meanings in German are taken from the above dictionary and the translations are authorial.

particular radio or television tubes (*Elektronenröhre, besonders Radio- oder Fernsehröhre*) 4b. Fluorescent tube, neon tube (*Leucht[stoff]röhre, Neonröhre*) 5. Screen, TV (*Bildschirm, Fernsehgerät*) 6. underground passage of a tubular building (*röhrenförmiger unterirdischer Gang eines Baus*)

Narrowing of meaning within the semantic field is a rare phenomenon, and it is often difficult to precisely determine the extent of its reduction. These loanwords have already undergone a reduction in the number of meanings, but they also exhibit a restricted usage within a specific context. In our corpus, examples illustrating this type of narrowing include *šolja, brile, and gemišť*.

For instance, the replica *šolja* < *Schale* in German, according to Duden, has eleven different meanings. Among other things, it refers to *a bowl with a hemispherical shape*. However, in Bosnian, the semantic field has been narrowed, and the word *šolja* is used exclusively to mean a "small container with a handle from which coffee or tea is drunk."

Additionally, to emphasize the smaller size of this container, Bosnian frequently uses the diminutive form *šoljica*, whereas in German, the word *Schale* is not used for this meaning. This transformation clearly illustrates the process of semantic narrowing within a specific field.

Expansion of meaning

In the secondary phase of integration, a loanword can retain its original meaning but can also develop new meanings that did not exist in the donor language.

This process is known as expansion of meaning, where the word loses some of its precision but gains greater semantic flexibility (Filipović, 1986: 169–170).

For meaning expansion to occur, two fundamental conditions must be met:

1. Complete phonological, morphological, and semantic integration of the word into the recipient language.
2. Unrestricted use in everyday communication within the recipient language.

Since this phenomenon occurs only after the word has been fully adapted to the recipient language, expansion of meaning is considered an exclusive feature of secondary adaptation.

Secondary semantic adaptation includes:

Expansion in the number of meanings (adding new meanings to a word).

Expansion of the semantic field (broadening the word's usage to new contexts).

Filipović (1985:179), drawing on Hope's theory, identifies four primary types of meaning change:

- Metaphor – when a word acquires a new meaning based on similarity to the original concept.
- Metonymy – when a meaning develops through a logical or functional association with an existing meaning.
- Folk etymology – when a new meaning arises due to similarity in form with another word.
- Ellipsis – when part of a compound phrase is omitted, and the remaining word takes on a new meaning.

These types of changes represent key mechanisms through which loanwords in the recipient language develop new meanings, becoming an integral part of the broader lexical system.

Metaphorical Expansion and Pejoration

To illustrate the influence of metaphor in semantic adaptation, we can examine the German loanword *šlauf* < *Schlauch*. In its primary adaptation phase, two meanings were transferred from German: "hose" and "swimming belt". The second meaning served as the basis for further expansion, leading to the creation of a new metaphorical meaning in Bosnian—"fat deposits around the waist".

Additionally, the phrase "gutanje šlaufa" (literally "swallowing the hose") emerged in medical terminology, referring to "the insertion of a tube-shaped medical instrument for a gastroscopic examination". In Bosnian, the loanword *šlauf* is used with all three meanings. While the first two were transferred in primary adaptation and became frequent in usage, the word's productivity within the Bosnian linguistic system facilitated the development of a new metaphorical meaning.

Beyond the potential for metaphorical meaning, a word may remain neutral in connotation or acquire a pejorative nuance. In most cases, metaphorization is followed by pejoration. In our corpus, the Germanism *šlauf*, when used in the sense of "fat deposits around the waist", is predominantly employed with a pejorative connotation.

Metonymic Expansion

One example of a loanword whose meaning expanded under the influence of metonymy is the Germanism *štapići*, referring to elongated salty snacks.

The German loanword *štap* < *Stab* was borrowed into Bosnian with the meaning "rod" or "a tool for work or walking". In this form and with these meanings, the word *štap* became fully integrated and functionally equivalent to native words, making it susceptible to further semantic changes.

By adding the diminutive suffix *-ić*, common in Bosnian, the new word *štapić* (singular) was formed. Further modification with the plural suffix *-i* created *štapići*, which acquired the new meaning of "elongated stick-shaped snacks".

The term *štapići* is now widely used in various compound words, where it conveys the meaning of "something shaped like a small stick", as seen in examples such as:

- *riblji štapići* (fish sticks),
- *čarobni štapić* (magic wand),
- *dirigentski štapić* (conductor's baton)...

This development demonstrates how metonymy, through the association of form and function, plays a significant role in the semantic adaptation of loanwords within the recipient language.

Ellipsis in Semantic Adaptation

Ellipsis involves the omission of certain elements from a word or phrase. In the case of German loanwords in our corpus, this process is most commonly observed in compound words, where the full meaning is transferred, but a part of the original term is omitted already in the primary phase during the formation of the replica.

For example, in the Germanism *rerma* < *Backröhre*, the first part of the compound (Back- meaning baking) has been omitted, while the second part (Röhre meaning tube/oven) has been retained as the primary lexical unit.

Conversely, some loanwords demonstrate the omission of the second part of the compound word, as seen in:

- *šlag* < *Schlagsahne*, where Sahne (cream) was omitted, while Schlag (whipped) was retained.
- *rendgen* < *Röntgengerät*, where Gerät (device/apparatus) was omitted, leaving only Röntgen, which originally referred to Wilhelm Röntgen, the physicist who discovered X-rays.

These examples illustrate how ellipsis functions as a key mechanism in the semantic adaptation of German loanwords, allowing for simplification while preserving the core meaning of the original term.

CONCLUSION

The classification of German loanwords according to thematic fields has confirmed that Germanisms are highly present and frequent in the conceptual domain of food and health. Based on this, a corpus of 68 German loanwords was compiled and analyzed with regard to their semantic adaptation processes.

The results of the study indicate that semantic adaptation in this field is significantly more complex than phonological or morphological adaptation. Unlike these more mechanical processes, semantic adaptation reflects the linguistic creativity of speakers. The analysis of primary adaptation confirms that most Germanisms were incorporated into Bosnian with their original, concrete meanings, such as *birtija*, *brezla*, *celer*, *griz*, etc. Within the analyzed corpus, narrowing of meaning was observed in eleven Germanisms, while three cases exhibited further restrictions within their semantic field.

Unlike primary adaptation, which has a clearly defined beginning and end, secondary adaptation begins with the formation of a primary replica based on the primary model but lacks a fixed endpoint. Borrowed words continue to evolve within the Bosnian language, with their changes occurring independently of German. This is demonstrated by examples of Germanisms that underwent meaning expansion in the secondary phase through metaphor, metonymy, pejoration, folk etymology, and ellipsis.

Among the nineteen Germanisms that experienced semantic shifts in the secondary phase, five were modified through metaphor, while isolated cases of meaning expansion via metonymy and folk etymology were also recorded.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that a Germanism undergoing secondary adaptation becomes a new model, capable of generating new lexemes and meanings. Consequently, the process of secondary adaptation can be considered ongoing, as long as the Germanism remains actively used in the Bosnian language.

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